

GUDUCCHI AS IMMUNOMODULATOR IN PEDIATRIC AGE GROUP***¹Vd. Rabiya Shirgave, ²Vd. Archna Nikam**¹Asst. Prof. Dept. of Rachana Sharir Shubhangi Patil Ayurved College Ichalkaranji.s²Prof. and HOD Dept. of Kaumarbhritya Government Ayurveda College Nagpur.

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ABSTRACT

Immunity is the power of body to fight against the disease. According to Ayurveda Immunity is Vydhikshmatav that means bala against vydhi or vyadhiptibandtav. If a person has best immunity then he can deal with any type of disorder sudden cause of any disease, from minute disease like cough, cold up to major disease like AIDS, leprosy Diabetes, Tuberculosis, Hypertension and now a days covid -19 pandemic all can occur if and only if the immunity of person is affected and vice –versa. AWhereas children they are more prone to respiratory disease and many of suffering from delayed milestone, sickle cell disorder. According to Ayurveda balya awstha is kapha awstha it means children are more prone to kaphaj vydhi. In Ayurvedic literature there is tremendous information related with medicinal plant is available out of which Guduchhi is one of the plant which act on immunity by

its Kattu, Tikt, Kashya Rasa and Madhur Vipak and also it is said to be Rasayani by their Gun-Karma so here in this article we are analyzing whether it can act as best immunomodulator in Pediatric age group as children having good quality of immunity.

KEYWORDS: Guduchhi, Immunity, Immunomodulator, Different age groups.**INTRODUCTION**

Immunity can be defined as, a complex biological system endowed with the capacity to recognize and tolerate whatever belongs to the self , and to recognize and reject what foreign (non –self).In biology, immunity is the capability of multicellular organisms to resist harmful microorganism immunity involves both specific and nonspecific components. The non-

